

Chlorophyll contents of *Baliospermum montanum* (Willd.) Muell. Arg under the influence of IAA, Brassinolide, Thiourea and Potassium nitrate

Fatima Khan* and Mudasir Qadir

Govt. College of Science and Commerce Benazeer, Bhopal-462008 (India)
Correspondence email: muddassirahmad62@gmail.com

Abstract

In this investigation, the seeds of *B. montanum* were studied for their chlorophyll contents which were pretreated with IAA, Brassinolide, Thiourea and Potassium nitrate before germination. The highest chlorophyll contents were found to be in brassinolide treated seeds followed by those treated with IAA, thiourea and potassium nitrate. The respective amount of chlorophyll under these treatments was found to be 5.80 mg-g FW⁻¹ under 10 ppm concentration of brassinolide, it was followed by 5.58 mg-g FW⁻¹ under 100 ppm IAA, 5.47 mg-g FW⁻¹ under 10 ppm thiourea, 5.28 mg-g FW⁻¹ under potassium nitrate and 4.99 mg-g FW⁻¹ in the seedlings raised from untreated seeds. The mentioned results concluded that the primary productivity of this chosen plant increases with lower doses of brassinolide as compared to controlled seedlings as well as other used factors.

Baliospermum montanum is a shrub of the family Euphorbiaceae and commonly known as Danti. Its twigs are used as tooth brush by villagers in Raisen district and adjoining areas. The plant grows in dry places, often in phosphorus rich soils. There is scanty flowering and fruiting. Because of the thick seed coat, germination of seeds under natural conditions is often very poor.

In the present investigation, the seeds of *B. montanum* were subjected to various treatments which are mentioned above to enhance its germination and also to check the

impact of these treatments on its primary productivity. Studies on germination, dormancy and the primary productivity have been carried out by various workers which include *In vitro* propagation of *Abrus precatorius* L. A Rare Medicinal Plant of Chittagong Hill Tracts by Animesh *et al.*,¹ Monago & Nwodo⁸ have investigated Antidiabetic effect of crude trigonelline of *Abrus precatorius* Linn seed in alloxan diabetic rabbits. Phytopharmacological evaluation of ethanolic extract of the seeds of *Abrus precatorius* Linn has studied by Rashmi *et al.*,¹² Bhatia *et al.*,⁴ have worked on *Abrus precatorius* (L.): An evaluation of

* Present address: Department of Botany, Govt. College Nusrullah Gunj-466331 (India).

traditional herb. Chemical constituents of *Abrus precatorius* have studied by Ragasa *et al.*,¹¹. Leбри *et al.*,⁶ have worked on Phytochemical analysis and *in vitro* anticancer effect of aqueous extract of *Abrus precatorius* Linn. Pharmacological activities of *Abrus precatorius* (L.) seeds have reported by Prabha M *et al.*,¹⁰. Similarly Okhale & Nwanosike⁹, have reported phytochemistry, ethnomedicinal uses, ethnopharmacology and pharmacological activities of *Abrus precatorius* Linn.

Antibacterial, antioxidant, and phenolic compound analyses of *Abrus precatorius* seed coat extract and its different fractions have been investigated by Mobin *et al.*,⁷. Vyas¹⁵ has studied Changes in Seedling Growth and Biochemical Contents in *Abrus precatorius* L. Under Nickel Treatment and development of random amplified polymorphic DNA markers for authentication of *Baliospermum montanum* Willd. leaf with its pharmacognostical evaluation has carried out by Rout *et al.*,¹³. Pharmacognostic, phytochemical analysis and antidiabetic activity of dried leaves of *Abrus precatorius* have studied by Boggula *et al.*,⁵. Bhakta, *et al.*,² have investigated Herbal contraceptive effect of *Abrus precatorius*, *Ricinus communis*, and *Syzygium aromaticum* on anatomy of the testis of male Swiss albino mice. The medicinal values of *Abrus precatorius* have also been reported by Bhakta, & Das³. And also Uddin, *et al.*,¹⁷ have investigated the Seasonal Effects on Photosynthetic Pigments, Nutrients, Flavonoids, Polyphenol and Antioxidant Activity of *Abrus precatorius* L. (Kunch).

Healthy seeds of *B. montanum* were

collected. The seeds were washed with running tap water three to four times and once surface sterilized with 0.1% H₂CL₂ solution for 5 minutes to remove the surface adhering microbes. After surface sterilization, the seeds were again washed with double distilled water. Uniform sized seeds were then transferred to sterilized Petri Plates provided with filter paper pads. Three replicates of treated and control seeds were kept for germination studies. The filter paper pads were moistened as and when needed. The emergence of radical was taken as germination.

The leaves of the treated as well as untreated plants were subjected to the chlorophyll estimation at regular intervals preferably fortnightly by the method given by Arnon (1949). For the estimation of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and total chlorophyll contents weighed amount of the leaves was taken and a paste was made in acetone in a clean mortar. It was finely ground with the help of pestle and filtered through a Buchner funnel under suction. The process was repeated till the residue became colourless and devoid of chloroplast pigments. The volume of the filtrate was adjusted to 100 ml by adding sufficient quantity of 80% acetone. The filtrate was subjected to spectrophotometric calculation of optical densities. The optical density was measured at 645 nm, 652 nm & 663 nm. The calculation of chlorophyll amount was made on the basis of per gram of leaf tissue and expressed in milligrams.

Brassinolide was found to enhance the chlorophyll contents of *B. montanum* to the tune of 5.80 mg-g FW⁻¹ under its 10 ppm concentration, it was followed by 5.58 mg-g FW⁻¹ under 100 ppm IAA, 5.47 mg-g FW⁻¹

Table-1. Effect of various factors on the chlorophyll contents of *B. montanum*

Treatments	Chlorophyll a (mg-g Fw)	Chlorophyll b (mg-g Fw)	Total Chlorophyll (mg-g Fw)
Control	2.97	2.02	4.99
IAA 10 ppm	3.07	2.09	5.16
IAA 50 ppm	3.19	2.17	5.36
IAA 100 ppm	3.27	2.31	5.58
Brassinolide 10 ppm	3.15	2.19	5.34
Brassinolide 50 ppm	3.37	2.43	5.8
Brassinolide 100 ppm	2.78	1.87	4.65
Thiourea 10 ppm	3.22	2.25	5.47
Thiourea 50 ppm	3.02	2.38	5.4
Thiourea 100 ppm	2.48	2.16	4.64
Potassium nitrate 10 ppm	3.15	1.89	5.04
Potassium nitrate 50 ppm	3.27	2.01	5.28
Potassium nitrate 100 ppm	2.78	1.69	4.47

under 10 ppm thiourea, 5.28 mg-g FW⁻¹ under potassium nitrate and 4.99 mg-g FW⁻¹ in the seedlings raised from untreated seeds.

The above observed results concluded that in case of potassium nitrate, the higher doses increase the primary productivity of *B. montanum* while the lower and moderate doses decrease the primary productivity of this medicinally important plant by decreasing its chlorophyll contents. In case of thiourea, lower doses enhance its primary productivity while moderate and higher doses decreased its primary productivity but in case of IAA, the higher doses result in the increment of its primary productivity while its lower and moderate doses result in the decline of the primary productivity of this plant and finally in case of brassinolide, moderate doses increase the primary productivity while its lower and

higher doses exhibit decreased amount of chlorophyll contents comparatively but this is the only factor which exhibited highest amount of chlorophyll contents among all the factors hence increased primary productivity.

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